

Schiff bases of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione with aliphatic diamines and their metal complexes

K. Krishnankutty^a, P. Sayudevi^b and Muhammed Basheer Ummathur^{c*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Calicut-673 635, Kerala, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, NSS College, Manjeri-676 122, Kerala, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Unity Women's College, Manjeri-676 122, Kerala, India

E-mail : mbummathur@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 23 July 2007, revised 8 October 2007, accepted 12 October 2007

Abstract : Reaction of aliphatic diamines [1,2-diaminoethane, 1,3-diaminopropane and 1,6-diaminohexane] with 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione yielded a new series of polydentate Schiff base ligands. The existence of these compounds predominantly in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded keto-imine form has been well demonstrated from their analytical, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. Dibasic tetradentate N₄ coordination of the compounds in their [ML] complexes [M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}] has been established on the basis of analytical and spectral data.

Keywords : 3-(2-Thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione, Schiff base, keto-imine, IR spectra, ¹H NMR spectra, mass spectra.

Introduction

The polydentate Schiff bases are well known to coordinate with various metal ions to form metallic complexes with theoretical and practical applications of different types¹. A large number of macrocyclic ligands having imine linkages can be synthesized by the reaction between dicarbonyl compound and diamines². These ligand systems have gained considerable importance because of their utility as model compounds in bioinorganic studies as well as their potential as catalysts in many reactions³. They find application in the determination of transition metal ions⁴⁻⁶, in the study of acid-base equilibrium, acidity constants values^{4,7} and for analytical purposes^{4,8}. Although the coordination compounds of Schiff bases of 1,3-diketones have been extensively studied⁹, little attention has been paid to Schiff bases derived from arylazo derivatives of 1,3-diketones. Besides having wide application as yellow dyes and pigments¹⁰ the arylazo-1,3-diketones have been extensively used as intermediates in the preparation of a large number of biologically important heterocyclic compounds, and as precursors of potential antidiabetic drugs³. In continuation of our studies on arylazo derivatives of 1,3-diketones¹¹⁻¹⁵, we report herein the synthesis and characterization of a new series of Schiff bases produced from 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione with

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of H₂bte, H₂btP, H₂bth and their metal complexes

Compd./ Empirical formula	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	M
H ₂ bte	70	85	48.88 (48.43)	4.74 (4.93)	24.98 (25.11)	-
C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂ H ₂ btP	74	70	49.50 (49.57)	5.16 (5.22)	24.18 (24.35)	-
C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂ H ₂ bth	72	98	52.48 (52.59)	5.74 (5.98)	22.20 (22.31)	-
C ₂₂ H ₃₀ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂ [Ni(bte)]	76	278	42.70 (42.97)	3.74 (3.98)	22.19 (22.28)	11.52 (11.68)
C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₈ NiO ₂ S ₂ [Ni(btp)]	70	242	43.94 (44.13)	4.22 (4.26)	21.82 (21.68)	11.44 (11.36)
C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₈ NiO ₂ S ₂ [Ni(bth)]	72	242	47.64 (47.25)	5.02 (5.01)	20.12 (20.05)	10.64 (10.51)
C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₈ NiO ₂ S ₂ [Cu(bte)]	75	298	42.68 (42.56)	3.84 (3.94)	21.92 (22.07)	12.40 (12.52)
C ₁₈ H ₂₀ CuN ₈ O ₂ S ₂ [Cu(btp)]	70	266	43.51 (43.72)	4.11 (4.22)	21.35 (21.47)	11.98 (12.18)
C ₁₉ H ₂₂ CuN ₈ O ₂ S ₂ [Cu(bth)]	74	286	46.71 (46.85)	4.91 (4.97)	20.05 (19.87)	11.34 (11.28)
C ₂₂ H ₂₈ CuN ₈ O ₂ S ₂ [Zn(bte)]	68	260	42.56 (42.41)	3.91 (3.93)	21.92 (21.99)	12.61 (12.83)
C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂ Zn [Zn(btp)]	70	280	43.58 (43.56)	4.08 (4.20)	21.20 (21.40)	12.64 (12.49)
C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂ Zn [Zn(bth)]	72	280	46.98 (46.70)	4.82 (4.95)	20.00 (19.81)	11.74 (11.56)

aliphatic diamines; 1,2-diaminoethane, 1,3-diaminopropane and 1,6-diaminohexane. Typical metal complexes of these ligand systems were also studied.

Results and discussion

The Schiff bases H₂bte, H₂btP and H₂bth are formed in good yield by the condensation of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione with 1,2-diaminoethane, 1,3-diaminopropane and 1,6-diaminohexane. Elemental analysis data (Table 1) of the compounds suggest that the condensation of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione with diamines occurred in the 2 : 1 ratio as in structure 1 (Scheme 1). The compounds are crystalline in nature and are insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents like benzene, CCl₄, petroleum ether, chloroform and acetone. They formed well defined and crystalline complexes with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions. The analytical data (Table 1) together with non-electrolytic nature in DMF (specific conductance < 10 Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹; 10⁻³ M solution) suggest [ML] stoichiometry of the complexes.

Scheme 2

The Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} chelates are diamagnetic while Cu^{II} complexes showed normal paramagnetic moment. The observed electronic, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data of the complexes are fully consistent with structure 2 (Scheme 2).

Table 2. Characteristic IR stretching frequencies (cm^{-1}) of H_2bte , H_2btp , H_2bth and their metal complexes

Compd.	C=O	C=N	M-N
H_2bte	1680	1630, 1620, 1615	-
$[\text{Ni}(\text{bte})]$	1678	1626, 1613, 1576	548, 532
$[\text{Cu}(\text{bte})]$	1675	1625, 1612, 1570	555, 538
$[\text{Zn}(\text{bte})]$	1675	1628, 1614, 1577	542, 530
H_2btp	1672	1628, 1618, 1612	-
$[\text{Ni}(\text{btp})]$	1672	1624, 1610, 1564	545, 530
$[\text{Cu}(\text{btp})]$	1670	1623, 1610, 1572	550, 535
$[\text{Zn}(\text{btp})]$	1670	1625, 1610, 1568	535, 525
H_2bth	1665	1627, 1618, 1612	-
$[\text{Ni}(\text{bth})]$	1665	1615, 1612, 1579	530, 518
$[\text{Cu}(\text{bth})]$	1663	1622, 1609, 1566	538, 512
$[\text{Zn}(\text{bth})]$	1664	1624, 1610, 1582	538, 522

Infrared spectra : The IR spectra of the Schiff bases in the $1600\text{--}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region showed four strong bands at ~ 1670 , 1630 , 1620 and 1615 cm^{-1} . The band at $\sim 1670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to conjugated free acetyl carbonyl¹⁶. The remaining three bands are due to C=N of hydrazone, imine and thiazole groups¹⁷. A prominent band appeared at $\sim 1540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to NH deformation vibration. Several medium intensity bands appeared in the $1580\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region of the spectra are due to the stretching of various C=C vibrations. That the compounds exist in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded form¹⁸ is clearly evident from the broad band appeared in the region $2300\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the IR spectra of all the complexes the strong band at $\sim 1670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to conjugated free acetyl carbonyl group of the ligand remain unaffected indicating its non-involvement in complexation. The strong band at $\sim 1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the free ligand due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ (imine) shifted to low wave number and appeared as a prominent band in the $1550\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The hydrazone and thiazole $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ are only marginally affected in the spectra of all the complexes. These indicate that the imine and one of the hydrazone nitrogens are involved in bonding with the metal ion¹⁹ as in structure 2. The replacement of the NH proton by metal ion is clearly indicated from the disappearance of the NH deformation band of the free ligand at $\sim 1540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the complexes. The broad band in the region $2300\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ cleared up in the spectra of all the complexes confirming the replacement of the hydrogen bonded NH proton by metal ion. The presence of new medium intensity bands appeared in the $500\text{--}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region assignable

Table 3. ^1H NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) of H_2bte , H_2btp , H_2bth and their Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes

Compd.	NH	Thiazolyl	$(\text{CH}_2)_n$	CH_3
H_2bte	9.44 (2H)	7.26 (2H) 7.06 (2H)	3.86 (4H)	2.26 (6H) 2.47 (6H)
H_2btp	9.63 (2H)	7.32 (2H) 7.16 (2H)	2.87 (2H) 3.80 (4H)	2.22 (6H) 2.54 (6H)
H_2bth	9.58 (2H)	7.14 (2H) 7.24 (2H)	3.20 (8H) 3.40 (4H)	2.35 (6H) 2.56 (6H)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{bte})]$	-	7.28 (2H) 7.10 (2H)	3.90 (4H)	2.28 (6H) 2.54 (6H)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{btp})]$	-	7.36 (2H) 7.16 (2H)	2.91 (2H) 3.86 (4H)	2.28 (6H) 2.58 (6H)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{bth})]$	-	7.18 (2H) 7.26 (2H)	3.26 (8H) 3.42 (4H)	2.38 (6H) 2.60 (6H)
$[\text{Zn}(\text{bte})]$	-	7.26 (2H) 7.12 (2H)	3.88 (4H)	2.26 (6H) 2.56 (6H)
$[\text{Zn}(\text{btp})]$	-	7.34 (2H) 7.18 (2H)	2.93 (2H) 3.84 (4H)	2.26 (6H) 2.57 (6H)
$[\text{Zn}(\text{bth})]$	-	7.16 (2H) 7.24 (2H)	3.24 (8H) 3.44 (4H)	2.36 (6H) 2.62 (6H)

to $\nu\text{M-N}$ in the spectra of all the complexes¹⁸ also support structure 2. Important bands that appeared in the spectra are given in Table 2.

^1H NMR spectra : In the ^1H NMR spectra of the Schiff bases, no signals were observed above $\delta 10$ ppm assignable to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded $\text{N-H}\cdots\text{O}=\text{C}/\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{N}$ groups of the keto-hydrazone/azo-enol forms typical of arylazo derivatives of acetyl-acetone¹²⁻¹⁵. The spectra of all the compounds show a two proton signal at $\sim\delta 9.50$ ppm due to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded $\text{N-H}\cdots\text{N}$ protons²⁰. The methylene and thiazolyl protons show signals at positions as expected. The spectra showed two six-proton singlets at $\delta 2.20\text{--}2.60$ ppm due to methyl groups. The integrated intensities of all the signals agree well with the structure 1 of the compounds. In the ^1H NMR spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, signal due to the NH protons of the free ligand disappeared indicating the replacement of these protons by metal ions. Integrated intensities of all other protons agree well with the 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry of the complexes as in structure 2 (Table 3).

Mass spectra : The mass spectra of all the compounds show the molecular ion peak corresponding to their formulation. Peaks due to the elimination of

CH₃CO⁺ and thiazole groups from the molecular ion are observed in all the spectra^{15,21}. The FAB mass spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes showed molecular ion peaks of appreciable intensity corresponding to [CuL] stoichiometry. Peaks correspond to L⁺ and fragments of L⁺ are also present in the spectra. Other prominent peaks are due to the elimination of CH₃CO⁺ and thiazole groups from the parent ion. The spectra of all the chelates contain a number of fragments containing copper in the 3 : 1 natural abundance of ⁶³Cu and ⁶⁵Cu isotopes. Important fragments appeared in the spectra are given in Table 4.

Electronic spectra : The UV spectra of the Schiff bases show two broad bands with maxima at ~370 nm and ~260 nm due to the various $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. In complexes these absorption maxima shifted appreciably to low wave numbers. The Cu^{II} complexes showed a broad visible band, λ_{\max} at ~15000 cm⁻¹. This, together with the measured μ_{eff} values (~1.74 B.M.) suggests the square-planar geometry²². In agreement with this, spectra recorded in pyridine, a broad band centered at ~11000 cm⁻¹ was observed which indicates the formation of octahedral pyridine adducts. The observed diamagnetism and broad medium-intensity band at ~17500 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the Ni^{II} chelates suggest their square-planar geometry. In conformity, the spectra of the chelates in pyridine solution (10⁻³ M) showed three bands corresponding to configurational change to octahedral due to the association of pyridine. The three well-separated absorption bands at

λ_{\max} ~8300, ~13500 and ~24300 cm⁻¹ correspond to the transitions; $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}$, $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$ (F) and $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$ (P) respectively.

Experimental

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen percentages were determined by microanalyses (Heraeus Elemental analyzer) and metal contents of complexes by AAS (Perkin-Elmer 2380). The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded in methanol solution (10⁻⁴ M) on a 1601 Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr discs) on an 8101 Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆) on a Varian 300 NMR spectrometer and mass spectra on a Jeol/SX-102 mass spectrometer (FAB using Argon and *meta*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix). Molar conductance of the complexes was determined in DMF at 28 ± 1 °C using solution of about 10⁻³ M concentration. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on a Guoy type magnetic balance.

Synthesis of H₂bte, H₂btp and H₂bth : 3-(2-Thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione was prepared as reported¹². An ethanolic solution of the diamine (0.01 mol in 20 mL) was added to an ethanolic solution of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione (0.02 mol, 20 mL) and stirred for ~5 h in a closed vessel maintaining the temperature at 60–65 °C, evaporated at reduced pressure and the crystalline compound formed was filtered and recrystallized from hot methanol to get chromatographically (tlc) pure compound.

Synthesis of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes : An ethanolic solution of metal(II) acetate (0.01 mol, 20 mL) was added to an ethanolic solution of the ligand (0.01 mol, 20 mL) and the mixture refluxed on a water bath for ~2 h. The solution was kept overnight at room temperature and added to crushed ice, containing ~1 g sodium acetate to maintain the pH around 6. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with excess of water, recrystallized from hot ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Conclusion :

Three new Schiff base ligands have been prepared by the condensation of 3-(2-thiazolylazo)-2,4-pentanedione with 1,2-diaminoethane, 1,3-diaminopropane and 1,6-diaminohexane. Analytical, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data revealed a 2 : 1 product in which one of the carbonyl group of the diketone is involved in Schiff base formation. Analytical, physical and spectral data of the [ML] complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} showed

Table 4. Mass spectral data of H₂bte, H₂btp, H₂bth and their Cu^{II} complexes

Compd.	Mass spectral data (m/z)
H ₂ bte	446, 362, 278, 403, 360, 319, 235, 192
C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	
H ₂ btp	460, 376, 292, 417, 374, 333, 249, 206
C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	
H ₂ bth	502, 418, 334, 459, 416, 375, 291, 248
C ₂₂ H ₃₀ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	
[Cu(bte)]	509, 507, 425, 423, 341, 339, 466, 464, 423,
C ₁₈ H ₂₀ CuN ₈ O ₂ S ₂	421, 382, 380, 298, 296, 255, 253, 446, 360,
	192
[Cu(btp)]	523, 521, 439, 437, 355, 353, 480, 478, 437,
C ₁₉ H ₂₂ CuN ₈ O ₂ S ₂	435, 396, 394, 312, 310, 269, 267, 460, 376,
	206
[Cu(bth)]	565, 563, 481, 479, 397, 395, 522, 520, 479,
C ₂₂ H ₂₈ CuN ₈ O ₂ S ₂	477, 438, 436, 354, 352, 311, 309, 502, 291,
	248

the dibasic tetradentate N_4 coordination involving the imino and hydrazone nitrogens while the carbonyl groups are excluded from coordination.

References

1. S. A. Sadeek, *J. Argent. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **93**, 165; T. Benabdallah, A. H. Al-Taiar and H. Reffas, *S. Afr. J. Chem.*, 2004, **57**, 33; D. Kumar, A. Syamal and A. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 280.
2. N. Raman, Y. Pitchaikaniaraja and A. Kulandaisami, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 2001, **113**, 183; M. Alaudeen, A. Abraham and P. K. Radhakrishnan, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1995, **107**, 123.
3. H. J. Garg and C. Prakash, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1971, **60**, 323; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 1056.
4. C. S. Salazar and M. I. Toral, *J. Chil. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **49**, 169; M. S. Masoud, G. B. Mohamed, Y. H. Abdul-Razek, A. E. Ali and F. N. Khairy, *J. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **46**, 99.
5. F. G. Montelongo, V. G. Diaz and C. R. T. González, *Microchem. J.*, 1982, **27**, 194; F. Kai, Y. Sakanashi, S. Satoh and S. Uchikawa, *Anal. Lett.*, 1983, **16(A13)**, 1013.
6. M. I. Toral, P. Richter, N. Lara, M. T. Escudero and C. Soto, *Anal. Lett.*, 2000, **33**, 93.
7. V. G. Diaz, C. R. T. González and F. G. Montelongo, *Anales de Química*, 1983, **79**, 83.
8. J. J. Arias, F. Jiménez, A. I. Jiménez and F. G. Montelongo, *Anales de Química*, 1983, **79**, 248.
9. P. D. Benny, J. L. Green, H. P. Engelbrecht, C. L. Barnes and S. S. Jurisson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 2381; T. D. Thangadurai and K. Natarajan, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organic Chem.*, 2001, **31**, 549.
10. K. Venkataraman, "Chemistry of Synthetic Dyes", Academic Press, New York, 1977; R. R. Myers and J. L. Long, "Pigments", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1975, Part I.
11. K. Krishnankutty, P. Sayudevi and Muhammed Basheer Ummathur, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 337.
12. K. Krishnankutty and D. K. Babu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 379.
13. K. Krishnankutty and V. T. Rema, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organic Chem.*, 1995, **25**, 243.
14. K. Krishnankutty and John Michael, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1993, **70**, 238; 1993, **24**, 259; 1991, **22**, 327.
15. K. Krishnankutty and P. Ummer, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 194; 1988, **65**, 213.
16. L. J. Bellamy, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Chapman and Hall, London, 1980.
17. P. Gilli, V. Bertolasi, V. Ferretti and G. Gilli, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 1405.
18. N. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1997.
19. P. Viswanathamurthi, A. Geetha, R. Karvembu and K. Natarajan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 90.
20. N. Thankarajan and K. Krishnankutty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 401; D. C. Nonhebel and A. Mitchell, *Tetrahedron*, 1979, **35**, 2013.
21. H. Budzikiewicz, C. Djerassi and D. H. Williams, "Mass Spectrometry of Organic Compounds", Holden Day, San Francisco, 1967.
22. K. C. Joshi and V. N. Pathak, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **22**, 37.